
Intellectual Property Rights and its role in E-Commerce

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Abstract:

IPR in e-commerce is a highly valuable component of e-commerce. IPR stands for Intellectual Property Rights – the rights that allow a business to use their invention to gain financial benefits and market leadership, over its competitors. Despite its significant value, it is often neglected because most people fail to understand it and because its connections to e-commerce are not very obvious. Regardless, IP and E-commerce are entirely interdependent. E-commerce typically involves selling products or services based on Intellectual Property and its licensing. In the digital world, there are so many types of Intellectual Properties that can be traded through an e-commerce platform be it music, photographs, designs, pictures, software, content, and so much more. In all these scenarios, IPR is especially significant since the value of these goods need to be protected. The protection is afforded through tools such as Intellectual Property laws and technological security systems. If IP theft is rampant, it could potentially ruin an e-commerce business – which is why IPR in e-commerce is extremely crucial. This article takes you through the significance of IPR in retail as well as the elements that are protected under IPR.

Keywords: *Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), E – Commerce, Protection of Business*

Introduction:

What are Intellectual property Rights?

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) would refer to anything and everything that is the conception of the human mind which creates an exclusive right bestowed upon the person over the creations of their intellect. According to the Oxford Dictionary, “intellectual property is an intangible property as a result of human creativity.” Intellectual Property is of various kinds, few significant ones being Copyrights, Trademark and Patents. IPR also include inventions of a product or process, a start-up business, creating new music or lyrics of a song and many more.

What is E-Commerce?

Electronic Commerce or E-Commerce as simply told is where

commercial transactions are conducted through online mode. These would include conducting or establishing businesses, exchanging goods and services or both primarily over the internet. Examples For E-commerce would include platforms such as: Amazon, Swiggy, Zomato and so forth.

Research Methodology:

Information was collected from various secondary sources readily available. Various reports, research papers, case studies regarding role of intellectual property right were referred, apart from numerous journals and research papers. The in-depth analysis of various literatures has helped in framing the concept about intellectual property rights and its significance for E - commerce

Literature Review:

Several studies are there in existence on IPR and its various aspects.

Savale and Savale, 2016 have described that IPRs are necessary for protecting the inventions as well as upholding the standards of such inventions. It is desirable that those who are innovating should get the desired commercial benefits so that they can be encouraged enough for future innovations.

Jajpura et al., 2017 have discussed all forms of IPR in detail in the Indian context – beginning from Industrial Design to trademark and even geographic indications along with their needs, importance, functioning along with the regional laws. This study has also focused India's involvement in IPR filing compared to the rest of the World which signifies our development in this field.

Ravi, 2017 has discussed extensively about how the medicine industry has adjusted itself with the laws of IPRs and how it has helped this industry to grow both at the national as well as at the international levels. The Research done for this study establishes the status of IPR in certain medicinal businesses, and the findings suggest a certain upward trend by highlighting the need for more industry-wide awareness and IPR implementation.

Yang, 2018 has discussed about how the era of big data and its analysis are going to get a grip over the world and thus there are several major areas related to E – commerce that need to be protected by IPR. This paper also asks for developing a supervisory body or environment for developing IPRs related to the field of E-commerce only. This paper has also highlighted the fact that every nation, developed or developing, has online business facilities now- a-days and this fact should be considered with significance for developing E-commerce based IPRs.

Punam, 2018 has defined IPR as the desire for the public to grants rights over any

property based on innovations and creations and it extends over several socio-economic aspects. The author has also highlighted about different forms of IPRs and how they can provide commercial benefits to the creators of such innovations.

Gaikwad, 2020 in his study has covered the history, goals and several other aspects of IPR. The author has opined that creative expressions, innovations and ideas are the major areas based on which people or public are Hence, is famous for ready to confer the rights of property are known as IPR. Hence, IPR is famous for granting the rights to the developers or innovators of such properties to benefit commercially as well.

Sreeragi, 2021 has not only discussed about the forms of IPR but also gone onto connect IPRs with regional laws and opined that regional laws should be in collaboration with the innovations for enjoying privileges over such creations. This study explains about how inventions registered for a longer period of times will be protected legally.

This paper makes an effort to fill up that gap which is significant in the context of research in the coming days. Following section describes about the relevance of the present study.

How are IPR and E-commerce interlinked?

In today's world, economies are constantly growing and changing. Internet as such plays a vital role in the development of the same. That being the case, it is necessary to understand that IPR plays a crucial role in the process of conducting e-commerce business and its impact in the virtual world. It is necessary to keep a tab on E-commerce along with the technology infrastructure in such a manner that the value of the intellectual property is not disregarded. It is crucial than ever that there needs to be a constant process of improvement in this technicality of internet access.

Intellectual Property Rules:

IPR in E-commerce relates to buying and selling of goods and services via an online platform where as in retail it implies buying and selling of such goods and services by means of offline stores. Hence, it is necessary for the owners of E-commerce industries to safeguard their industries by the help of relevant IP laws. Following are E-Commerce areas that could well be covered by IP rules.

- a) Patent and various utility models cover or give safeguard to technologies, search engines, online platforms, etc.
- b) Depending on an economy's rules and regulations of IPR, specific software is protected under the Patent Law or the Copyrights Act and it incorporates safeguarding coding used by websites.
- c) Designing of website can be safeguarded by IPR or copyright laws.
- d) Documents shown on the websites, such as graphics; videos; written documents are covered by copyright act.
- e) Companies can use economy - based IPR laws for safeguarding their database. In the era of globalized world, several MNCs do follow this procedure.
- f) Companies can safeguard all forms of online elements – beginning from webpages and extending up to graphics – by means of different IP rules in different economies.
- g) Safeguarding website developments, its algorithm and coding, supply chain processes – everything does come under the purview of IPR.
- h) In developing economies like India, IPR regulations are effective in creation, development as well as upsurge in the numbers of E-commerce industries.

Intellectual Property Rights and its role in E-Commerce:

With constant improvements in the technological infrastructure of the internet, it's more important now than ever before to understand the role of Intellectual Property in e-commerce. There are four ways in which IPR in e-commerce is applicable:

1. **Safeguarding business interests of a company:** Intellectual Property Laws essentially safeguard the business interests of a company and its entities, typically against unfair competition. The absence of IP practices and laws, especially in this digital economy can result in several IPR violations. As such everything ranging from software to design and music can be stolen, duplicated and distributed all over the world, and the proprietors may go unrewarded for their unique creations. However, with laws pertaining to IPR in e-commerce, companies can secure their rights.
2. **Safeguarding essential components:** Intellectual Property law in e-commerce also helps protect critical technical and digital components owned by a company. These could be networks, routers, designs, software and chips and so on. These components are all different forms of intellectual properties that require protection, which in turn allow the internet to function smoothly. Keeping this in mind, IPR in E-commerce also safeguards essential components.
3. **Protecting products and patent licenses:** All online and e-commerce businesses are typically based on patent and product licensing. Since it takes several different technologies to create a product, most online companies choose to outsource the development of a few components or share their technologies using licensing agreements. The agreement

essentially consists of terms and conditions laid down for IPR protection.

4. **Safeguarding patent portfolios and trademarks:** For a business in the e-commerce space, Intellectual Property is its most valuable asset. Such a company typically owns a portfolio of patents and trademarks that help enhance the value of their business. IPR laws in e-commerce thus help safeguard these patents, portfolios and trademarks.

Importance of Intellectual Property in E-Commerce:

For most companies across the globe, their Intellectual Property is an asset that is far more valuable than any tangible asset owned by them. This is because Intellectual Property Laws protect companies from disclosing their trade secrets, while also protecting them against unfair competition.

The role of IPR in E-commerce is most clearly visible in today's digital economy. The presence of practices and statutes that govern the functioning of IP laws has encouraged new creations, while – also protecting the hard work put in by the creator. The law prevents others from stealing IPs and using it to their financial advantage, without paying the creator for the labour they put in, and their invention.

Protection of IPR under E-commerce:

IPR in retail and e-commerce deals with buying and selling products through a physical shop and a website, respectively. In retail also a owner needs to protect his intellectual property rights. It is no different that is for E-commerce and should various types of intellectual properties. The following states the usual IPR in E-commerce.

Various patent models protects E-commerce like search engines etc. Patent

Law or the Copyrights Act depends from country to country and their IPR laws may be divergent in application. Eg. A website design protected by copyright law. The copyright protection is available under the copyright law for the graphics, designs, materials, audio or video clippings, photographs etc. Therefore the companies in e-commerce world can protect their database under such copyright laws as applicable in their specific country.

Conclusion:

IPR in e-commerce helps companies that use online platforms. Intellectual property rights assist businesses in preserving and protecting their business operations as the internet retail market expands exponentially at the global level. IPR owners are able to claim a portion of the company's revenues because of IP rights in e-commerce. Hence, IPR in e-commerce safeguards e-commerce activities. However, the real application of IP Rights decides the success rate completely. The expansion of online commerce makes it easier for businesses to monitor and defend their trade activities, especially those who require maintaining anonymity. Intellectual property rights can be implemented with a focus on features which are unique and unavailable to others, successfully enabling E-commerce activity in the public domain. The legal protection of intellectual property rights promotes strength in the use of intellectual property, which helps not only in licensing, contracting, and outsourcing but also in developing new concepts and forming strategic alliances, all of which improve sales and e-commerce operations by introducing features which rivals cannot offer. This promotes healthy competition in online business and generates income for the rightful intellectual property owners. Because of this, intellectual property protects e-commerce and promotes economic justice.

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